

STABILITY – IN HARMONY

¹Tulibaev Hikmatulla Egamovich, ²Aripova Nasiba Atkhamovna, ³Halmamatova Lola
Amankulovna

¹ History teacher of the 9th general education school of Yangiyol city, Tashkent region,
Honorary professor of the Turan Academy of Sciences

^{2,3} Associate Professor of Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction

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Abstract. *This article provides a detailed understanding of the concepts of stability and change, and explains that socio-political stability is the foundation and guarantee of national unity, civil harmony, the renewal and reform of society, sustainable development and progress.*

Keywords: *stability, variability, history, philosophy, society.*

Introduction. The economic, political, spiritual stability and changeability of Central Asia, which is inhabited by peoples, folks and nations rich in natural resources in Asia and with common history, religion, customs and values, are of the main decisive factors of people's peaceful, free and prosperous life here, on one hand, the fate of relations between independent states existing in this region, on the other hand, and the issue of strategic balance in Eurasia, on the third.

If stability in Central Asia is implemented in the interests of all peoples, the bonds of friendship between states, peoples and nations will be so strong that any danger will be avoided, internal and external conflicts, and all kinds of threats will be put an end to. And people will be lucky to live in peace and quiet.

Accordingly, in our following scientific article, we aim to reveal the essence of the concepts of stability and variability, define them, and highlight how important these concepts are in the unique geopolitical space of Central Asia.

The logic of the development of the human world for several thousand years shows that stability and change are characteristic of every society, and at the same time it is one of the conditions of its existence.

So what is sustainability? This concept is defined in "Independence: an explanatory scientific and popular dictionary" as "Stability-peace-tranquility and creative work environment is a stable, continuous and firmly established stable condition. Stability is the basis and necessary condition of any creative activity. (Independence: explanatory scientific-popular dictionary. T. "Sharq", 1998, 18 p). In "Philosophy: an encyclopedic dictionary", "stability is peaceful harmony in society and the existence of conditions for its strengthening; the definition can be read as "a situation of solidarity between social strata, forces and political parties". Although these definitions are simple and concise, they do not reflect the philosophical and political aspects of the concept of sustainability.

According to the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language", the abstract noun "sustainability" is formed by adding the suffix "ility" to the word "sustain". The word "steady" expresses the meanings of: 1) determined, fixed, arranged; priority; 2) not affected by any change, always the same, unchanging, settled in one place, stable. And stability means "stability, solidity, unchanging state" of something, an event, a process, a phenomenon. So, we are talking about the state of things and events in existence that are relatively stable, solid, and gain priority. At this point, a question arises: what is the main factor that ensures such stability in society?

Stability is an integral system of certain socio-economic, political-legal, spiritual-cultural conditions that are relatively stable and prioritized in society, which are created due to the harmony of material and spiritual life, and which prepare the ground for positive change.

Based on the above philosophical definition, the following are the characteristics of sustainable development.

The first - harmony of material and spiritual life in society. If these two factors are not compatible, there will be no sustainable development in the society. Preferring material life over spiritual life leads society to chaos. History has witnessed this many times.

The second - interproportion between productive forces and production relations in the economic life of society, that is, harmony between production, consumption and distribution. Disproportion between them also creates various economic tensions and destabilizes the society.

The third - common views and even actions of political forces in society - parties, public organizations, mass social movements, non-governmental organizations and others regarding the organization and management of state power. Any disagreement, conflict, unhealthy environment between them, especially the illegal behavior of the opposition, seriously harms the sustainable development of society.

The fourth - cooperation and solidarity between social units in society - nation, religion and other strata. It is well known that inter-ethnic conflict or inter-religious enmity, racial discrimination or other disagreements lead to the disintegration of the state, the collapse of nations, the loss of their chosen path, and as a result, they fall into a vortex of instability and decline.

The fifth - mutuality of different ideas and ideologies representing the interests of different social strata in society. If there is no commonality between such ideas and ideologies in society, inevitable moral decay will occur. This, in turn, makes the ideological struggle more intense and destabilizes the society.

The sixth - recognition of mutually beneficial interstate cooperation and friendship with neighboring countries as a regional value. As long as the countries living in the same region do not establish mutually beneficial cooperation, they will never be able to ensure their sustainable development.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be said that stability prepares the ground for positive change and ensures rapid development of society.

An example of this is the current policy of Uzbekistan.

So what is mobility? Mobility is derived from the word "mobile" and means "to change from one state to another." Based on this dictionary meaning of the word mobility, it can be philosophically defined as an attribute of social reality as follows:

Mobility is the process of transition of things, events, phenomena from a certain state to another state due to the stable development of society in its socio-economic, political-legal, spiritual-cultural aspects of life.

Based on this definition, any stable development characterized by mobility is completed by the occurrence of some positive changes in society, that is, where there is stability, there is necessarily mobility. This mobility in turn creates a new stability. Therefore, stability is a characteristic inherent in mobility, inseparable from it. Mobility in society is widespread. It covers not only material and spiritual life in society, but also changes in human consciousness and thinking.

Mobility in society has a gradual nature, it arises on the ground of stability and manifests itself as its characteristic.

Any mobility is characterized by quantitative and qualitative measurements, and it is expressed by statistical indicators. Life is a dialectic. Because, if we compare the characteristics of stability and mobility, based on the methodological and important ideas that all events in life are closely connected with each other, firstly, stability refers to the specificity inherent in society, and mobility refers to their transition from a certain state to another state, and secondly, stability is always in a certain condition, will be available at the destination for a certain period of time.

Mobility applies where there is stability as their property. Stability and mobility can be classified according to their application in the life of society as follows:

Economic stability and mobility; Political stability and mobility; Socio-spiritual stability and mobility

There is no need to define each of these classifications. Because, based on the names of the classifications, it is possible to know what it is about. Every nation, folk, people, regardless of where they live on the globe, must perform the following tasks for their sustainable development.;

- Using advanced technologies in production, increasing labor productivity.
- Creating new jobs, reducing unemployment to a minimum
- Fight against poverty, helplessness, taking measures to end it
- Cutting the vein of corruption, which is a cancer in the society
- Activating public health care, improving the lifestyle of women and children, preventing the spread of various diseases
- Protecting and restoring nature, maintaining ecological balance
- Rational use of drinking water and economical use of water resources
- Prevention of various natural disasters, quick elimination of their consequences
- Prevention of local, regional, international conflicts and contradictions, and their peaceful resolution

-Religious tolerance, prevention and elimination of internal and external threats that threaten the peaceful coexistence of nations, peoples and states, etc.

Based on the above facts and considerations of our scientific article, we must conclude that socio-political stability is the foundation and guarantee of national unity, citizen harmony, sustainable development and progress, renewal and reform of society.

REFERENCES

1. З. Бзежински “Великая шахматная доска” М. 2005
2. И. Каримов “Хавфсизлик ва барқарор тараққиёт йўлида.Т.”Ўзбекистон”
3. Ҳ. Тулибаев Марказий Осиё ўзига хос геосиёсий минтақа” “Халқаро муносабатлар” №4, 2002
4. У. Хасанов Региональная безопасность и национальные интересы
5. Eldor Tulyakov Ҳаракатлар стратегияси билан беш йил: ислохотлар сарҳисоби // Strategy of Uzbekistan. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/arakatlar-strategiyasi-bilan-besh-yil-islo-otlar-sar-isobi> (дата обращения: 12.03.2023).
6. Эшмурадов Д. Э., Умарова И. Д. Вопросы организации дистанционного обучения в условиях самоизоляции //Теория и практика современной науки. – 2020. – №. 6. – С. 587-589.